

Journal of Veterinary Science and Research

Research Article

Open Access

Effect of antioxidants on lysozyme and complement activities in heat-stressed rabbits

Doaa Sayed Abdel-Hady¹, Yasser Kamal Badawi², Amany Sayed Maghraby³, Mahmoud Abdel-Latif^{4*}

¹Biotechnology Department, Animal Production Research Institute, Agriculture Research Centre, Beni-Suef, Egypt

²Biotechnology Department, Animal Production Research Institute, Agriculture Research Centre, Giza, Egypt

³Department of Therapeutic Chemistry, The Division of Pharmaceutical and Drug Industries Research, The Group of Immune and Biomarkers for Infection, (The Centre of Excellence for Advances Sciences), The National Research Centre, El Buhouth St., Dokki, Cairo, Egypt

⁴Immunity division, Zoology Department, Faculty of Science, Beni-Suef University, Beni-Suef, Egypt

*Corresponding Author: Mahmoud Abdel-Latif, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, Beni-Suef University, Beni-Suef, Egypt

Received Date: Jan 03, 2020 / Accepted Date: Jan 09, 2020 / Published Date: Jan 13, 2020

Abstract

The negative influence of heat stress (HS) on rabbit farms cannot be ignored. The current study aims to detect the effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (MOE), Vitamin C (Vit C) and sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) on HS-induced changes in the complement, lysozyme, and antioxidant activities. A total of 45 growing male NZW rabbits were divided into five groups: Negative control rabbits were not exposed to HS (group 1), while HS groups (2-5) were exposed to high temperatures (39°C). Group 2 was exposed to HS but non-treated while the rest of groups were treated with MOE, Vit C and NaHCO₃, respectively. Expression of lysozyme mRNA, as well as the activities of lysozyme, complement and antioxidants, were assayed. Serum IL-1 β was also assayed using ELISA. Furthermore, the histopathological changes of liver and kidney, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), body weight gain (BWG), and mortality rate of experimental animals, were investigated. Our data showed a decrease in lysozyme, antioxidant activities, and BWG versus increases in complement activity, IL-1 β level, and BUN in HS. Histological investigation showed an increase in inflammatory reactions. MOE, Vit C and NaHCO₃ could alleviate HS effects through increased activities of lysozyme and antioxidants versus decreased complement activity leading to improved health status.

Keywords: Heat stress; Lysozyme; Complement; Antioxidant; Immunity

Cite this article as: Doaa Sayed Abdel-Hady, Yasser Kamal Badawi, Amany Sayed Maghraby, et al. 2020. Effect of antioxidants on lysozyme and complement activities in heat-stressed rabbits. J Veterina Sci Res. 2: 01-18.

Copyright: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Copyright © 2020; Doaa Sayed Abdel-Hady

Effect of MOE, Vit C and NaHCO₃ on rabbit HS

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/jvsr.2020.110010>

JVSR: January-2020: Page No: 01-18

Please click on the full-length manuscript below links:

HTML: https://www.raftpubs.com/jvsr-veterinary-science-and-research/articles/jvsr_raft1010.php

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/jvsr.2020.110010>

ARCHIVES: <https://www.raftpubs.com/jvsr-veterinary-science-and-research/archive.php>